

Angelo Leogrande¹

Human Capital with Digital Skills in Europe

It grew by 8.83% between 2016 and 2021

The Desi Index calculates the value of the human capital between 2016 and 2021. Human Capital is calculated as a function consisting of the sum of two macro-variables: internet user skills and Advanced Skills and Development.

$$\mathbf{HumanCapital}_{it} = \mathbf{InternetUserSkills}_{it} + \mathbf{AdvancedSkillsAndDevelopment}_{it}$$

$$\mathbf{InternetUserSkills}_{it}$$

$$= \mathbf{AtLeastBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \mathbf{AboveBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \mathbf{AtLeastBasicSoftwareSkills}_{it}$$

$$\mathbf{AdvancedSkillsAndDevelopment}$$

$$= \mathbf{ICTSpecialists}_{it} + \mathbf{FemaleICTSpecialists}_{it} + \mathbf{EnterprisesProvidingICTTraining}_{it} + \mathbf{ICTGraduates}_{it}$$

Da cui deriva che

$$\mathbf{HumanCapital}_{it} = \mathbf{AtLeastBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \mathbf{AboveBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \mathbf{AtLeastBasicSoftwareSkills}_{it} + \mathbf{ICTSpecialists}_{it} + \mathbf{FemaleICTSpecialists}_{it} + \mathbf{EnterprisesProvidingICTTraining}_{it} + \mathbf{ICTGraduates}_{it}$$

Dove $i = 27$ e $t = [2016; 2021]$

Ranking of European nations by the value of human capital in 2021. Finland is in the first place for the value of human capital in Europe with a value of 17.78 units, followed by Sweden with a value of 16.14 and by Holland with a value of 15.39 units. In the middle of the standings there are France with a value of 11.84 units, followed by the Czech Republic with a value of 11.79 units and Croatia with a value equal to 11.68 units. Italy closes the ranking with a value of 8.78 units, followed by Romania with a value of 8.26 units and Bulgaria equal to a value of 8.18 units.

Ranking of European nations by value of human capital in the transition between 2016 and 2021. Poland is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of human capital between 2016 and 2021 with a value equal to 19.940% equal to an amount of 1,567 unit, followed by Greece with a value of 18.675% equal to an amount of 1.615 units and from Ireland with a value of 18.452% equal to an amount of 2.1 units. In the middle of the standings there are Croatia with a value of 10.219% equal to an amount of 1.083 units, followed by Slovenia with a value of 8.862% equal to an amount of 0.973 units, and from Finland with a value of 8.509% equal to an amount of 1,394 units. Bulgaria closes the ranking with a value equal to -0.618% equal to an amount of -0.051 unit, followed by Latvia with a value of -2.932% equal to an amount of -0.310 units and from Malta with a value equal to -3.401 % equal to an amount of -0.432 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows the presence of the following Clusters or:

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

- Cluster 1: Cyprus, Hungary, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Italy, Slovakia, Latvia, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Romania, Czech Republic, Croatia, France, Slovenia, Spain.
- Cluster 2: Netherlands, Germany, Estonia, Sweden, Denmark, Austria, Luxembourg, Finland, Malta, Belgium, Ireland.

Calculating the value of the median of Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 it appears that the value of human capital in the 2-C2 cluster has a median value of 14.04 units, while the corresponding value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to an amount of 10.60. It therefore follows that $C2 = 14.04 > C1 = 10.60$. It should be considered that from a geographical point of view, a contrast between the regions of the North Europe, especially Scandinavian, with high values of Human Capital, and the remaining regions of Europe which instead have very lower values of Human Capital, is evident. The traditional distinction between northern Europe and central-south Europe characterizes not only the distribution of income as much as the quality of human capital. And it cannot be excluded that there is a direct relationship between these two elements.

Network Analysis with Manhattan distance. A Network Analysis is created below using Manhattan's distance. Two structures were identified with complex networks and three simplified network structures. There is a complex structure between France, Spain, Croatia, and Slovenia. Particularly:

- France has a link with Spain for a value of 0.087 units, with Slovenia for a value of 0.045 units and with Croatia for a value of 0.21 units;
- Croatia has a connection with France for a value of 0.21 units, and a link with Slovenia having a value of 0.19 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Spain for a value of 0.097 units, with Croatia for a value of 0.19, and with France for a value of 0.045 units.
- Spain has a connection with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.097 units and with France equal to an amount of 0.87 units.

In addition, a further complex structure is detected between Germany, Austria, Luxembourg, and Estonia. The following links between the countries are:

- Luxembourg has a connection with Germany having a value of 0.25 units, and with Estonia having a value of 0.27 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Luxembourg with a value of 0.27 units and with Germany with a value of 0.13 units;
- Germany has a connection with Luxembourg for a value equal to an amount of 0.25 units, with Estonia for a value of 0.13 units and with Austria for a value of 0.23 units.

There are also three different simplified structures or:

- Slovakia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.2 units;
- Hungary has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.22 units;
- Italy has a connection with Poland for a value of 0.24 units.

Machine Learning and Predictions. A prediction with Machine Learning algorithms is created below. Algorithms are trained with 80% of the available data. Algorithms are optimized according to their ability to maximize R2 and minimize statistical errors or MSE, RMSE and Mae. Below is the order of the algorithms or:

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- SGD with a payoff value of 8;

- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 12;
- Adaboost and Random Forest with a payoff value of 18;
- Tree and KNN with a payoff value of 26;
- SVM with a payoff value of 32;
- Costant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

The best performer algorithm or the linear regression algorithm predicts a marginal reduction in the value of the human capital in the future equal to a value of -0.05%. Specifically there are countries for which the algorithm provides for a significant reduction in the value of human capital and these countries are:

- Romania with a percentage variation of -3.10% equivalent to an amount of -0.25 units;
- Greece with a percentage variation of -3.05% equivalent to an amount of -0.31 units;
- Finland with a percentage variation equivalent to an amount of -2.96% equal to an amount of -0.52 units.

However, there are also countries for which the algorithm predicts a significant growth in the value of human capital and these countries are:

- France with a variation equal to an amount of 2.23% equivalent to an amount of 0.26 units;
- Italy with a variation equal to an amount of 2.3% equal to a value of 0.20 units;
- Latvia with a percentage variation of 3.2% equal to a value of 0.33 units.

Conclusions. The value of human capital grew in the period between 2016 and 2021 in the countries of the Desi Index of an amount equal to about 8.8%. It should be considered that, however, human capital which is considered in this case refers above all to the dimension of digital knowledge. The indicator, in fact, does not consider the formation of human capital in non -scientific, humanistic, or artistic subjects. However, there are significant differences between northern Europe and the rest of Europe in the sense of human capital with digital skills. In this sense, it is necessary to intervene with economic policies that can be able to promote technological and digital skills at the population of the countries of southern Europe and Eastern Europe. In this sense, it should be considered that the development of human capital is necessary to develop the economy of knowledge and the economy of technological innovation in the context of competition between China and the USA.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

References

- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Massaro, A. (2022). The Determinants of Internet User Skills in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4113155*.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). The Role of Broadband Price Index in Fostering Economic Growth and Digitization in Europe. *Journal of Human, Earth, and Future*, 3(1), 32-54.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). *The Exports of Knowledge Intensive Services. A Complex Metric Approach*. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). International Scientific Co-Publications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4117970*.
- Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2022). *Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe* (No. 113008). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Massaro, A. (2022). ICT Specialists in Europe. *Available at SSRN*.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). e-Government in Europe. A Machine Learning Approach. *A Machine Learning Approach (February 25, 2022)*.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Broadband Price Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4036690*.
- Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN*.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3933407*.
- Leogrande, Angelo, and Alberto Costantiello. "Human Resources in Europe. Estimation, Clusterization, Machine Learning and Prediction." *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN (2021).

- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3930697*.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Intellectual Assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Broadband Penetration in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3953683*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The SMEs Innovation in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3964059*.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The Finance-Innovation Nexus in Europe. *IJISSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Friendly Environment in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3933553*.
- Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3964043*.
- Leogrande, Angelo, Alessandro Massaro, and Angelo M. Galiano. "The attractiveness of European research systems." *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* 4.10 (2020): 72-101.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Human Resources in European Countries During the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(9), 145-171.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Development of Green Technologies in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6549278>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Employment Impact of Innovation in Europe. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378058>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Turnover from Innovative Products in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6523444>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Environmental Sustainability in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6523934>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Fine Dust Pollution in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6525248>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Workers in the Knowledge Economy in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6380979>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6409233>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Registration of Trademarks in Europe. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6374376>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Export of High Knowledge Intensity Services of European Countries. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6467790>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). High Level Digital Skills in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6667031>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Digital Intensity in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6667556>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Application of Digital Technologies for Business in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6754503>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Turnover of e-Commerce of SMEs in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6756934>

Appendix

Evaluation Results

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
Linear Regression	0.052	0.228	0.196	0.991
SGD	0.157	0.396	0.334	0.972
Gradient Boosting	0.269	0.518	0.377	0.952
AdaBoost	0.373	0.611	0.489	0.934
Random Forest	0.523	0.723	0.451	0.907
Tree	0.718	0.847	0.651	0.873
kNN	0.719	0.848	0.612	0.872
SVM	1.171	1.082	0.683	0.792
Constant	6.119	2.474	1.969	-0.086
Neural Network	35.040	5.919	5.351	-5.220

2021	Feature 1	kNN	Tree	Random Forest	Gradient Boosting	SVM	Neural Network	Linear Regression	AdaBoost	Constant	SGD	Fold
17.7771	Finland	15.0231	15.6086	14.9454	16.138	13.6491	26.9792	17.2508	16.1389	11.8357	17.1148	1
13.5186	Ireland	12.6098	14.1119	13.3276	12.8012	12.8993	6.49607	13.7577	12.6954	11.8357	13.0323	1
11.8399	France	11.8077	12.1784	11.9755	11.8915	11.9466	3.23219	12.1048	11.9508	12.1583	11.9507	2
11.3915	Portugal	10.5579	11.8065	10.8623	10.7256	10.9174	5.12059	11.279	10.2773	12.1583	10.8714	2
13.3373	Austria	13.461	13.9636	13.6793	13.7369	13.9143	9.44942	13.4567	13.8103	12.1437	13.8763	3
10.2603	Greece	9.28342	9.93508	9.12064	9.59818	9.63896	9.04688	9.94708	9.4245	12.1437	9.51669	3
11.5356	Lithuania	11.1434	11.1648	11.3242	11.3243	11.2517	4.12169	11.4761	10.9381	12.0643	11.2124	4
14.046	Luxembourg	13.5682	13.7864	14.0618	13.8964	13.7484	8.99188	14.2521	13.8103	12.0643	13.8736	4
10.1201	Hungary	10.5571	9.97014	10.2758	10.1238	10.2728	6.57269	9.88701	10.2603	12.2047	10.2125	5
11.9508	Slovenia	11.7855	12.3508	11.9514	11.9429	11.9504	3.20185	12.0522	11.8399	12.2047	11.9975	5
12.6954	Belgium	12.7745	13.5554	12.4327	12.688	12.8221	5.26872	12.9605	13.3373	12.183	12.9557	6
9.9185	Cyprus	10.8525	11.2884	10.0716	10.6451	10.3681	6.34556	10.1022	10.2773	12.183	10.4244	6
8.17517	Bulgaria	9.36932	8.52084	9.08713	8.45249	9.94906	12.7139	8.21747	8.77885	12.289	8.45277	7
11.7883	Czechia	11.818	11.958	11.7416	11.6533	11.5909	3.89125	11.7793	11.6806	12.289	11.5598	7
10.2773	Latvia	10.7807	11.7111	10.2593	10.6532	10.8815	4.79935	10.6138	10.2603	12.1889	10.8016	8
8.26282	Romania	9.35179	8.47701	8.93827	8.17598	10.4041	15.0478	8.00649	8.17517	12.2664	7.93951	9
11.6806	Croatia	11.8396	11.8597	11.8168	11.8644	11.8309	3.16974	11.5923	11.9508	12.1349	11.8692	10
12.0832	Spain	11.759	12.1122	11.9009	11.9224	11.9557	3.25333	12.1827	11.7883	12.1195	11.9974	11
10.9381	Slovakia	10.9822	11.4635	10.8214	10.9729	11.0888	4.62235	10.7519	11.3915	12.1635	11.0556	12
12.2737	Malta	13.5682	13.1838	12.8059	13.1964	12.9277	6.45704	12.466	12.6954	12.1121	13.1136	13
16.1389	Sweden	15.3508	16.1547	15.1767	16.4557	14.7242	19.4874	16.06	15.3872	11.9635	16.0444	14
9.4245	Poland	9.45059	8.40562	9.71453	9.25015	9.74419	10.3729	9.15067	8.77885	12.2217	9.22039	15
14.4794	Estonia	13.2326	16.1507	13.8408	14.0458	13.8882	9.95385	14.068	13.8103	12.0273	13.9661	16
13.8103	Germany	13.3664	13.8453	14.5243	14.1976	14.0515	9.95556	14.041	14.046	12.053	13.9813	17
8.77885	Italy	9.24858	9.77229	9.56204	9.42269	9.6745	10.7159	8.98148	9.4245	12.2465	9.09584	18
15.3872	Netherlands	14.6131	16.4052	15.2855	15.1422	14.7867	14.8151	15.4348	15.2997	11.9924	15.1977	19
15.2997	Denmark	15.2902	16.4344	15.1856	15.857	14.5658	18.441	15.095	16.1389	11.9957	15.7719	20

	Algoritmo	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
1	Linear Regression	0.00000	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000
2	SGD	0.0030010	0.029520	0.026770	0.996941
3	Gradient Boosti...	0.0062021	0.050958	0.035112	0.993721
4	AdaBoost	0.0091746	0.067299	0.056838	0.990823
5	Random Forest	0.0134618	0.086979	0.049467	0.986476
6	Tree	0.0190351	0.108768	0.088264	0.981001
7	kNN	0.0190637	0.108944	0.080698	0.980840
8	SVM	0.0319824	0.150062	0.094471	0.967960
9	Constant	0.1734023	0.394658	0.343938	0.826598
10	Neural Network	1.00000	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000

Human Capital con Competenze Digitali in Europa

Countries	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Austria	★12,9	★13,42	★13,42	★13,49	★13,26	★13,34
Belgium	★11,92	★11,85	★12,34	★12,67	★12,84	★12,7
Bulgaria	★8,226	★7,602	★7,993	★8,312	★8,182	★8,175
Croatia	★10,6	★11,11	★11,32	★11,9	★11,59	★11,68
Cyprus	★9,483	★9,726	★10,05	★10,3	★9,989	★9,919
Czechia	★10,58	★10,19	★10,96	★11,28	★11,67	★11,79
Denmark	★15,18	★15,69	★14,73	★14,88	★15,07	★15,3
Estonia	★13,08	★12,75	★13,19	★13,63	★14,06	★14,48
Finland	★16,38	★16,32	★16,78	★16,5	★17,13	★17,78
France	★10,99	★11,07	★11,37	★11,49	★11,93	★11,84
Germany	★13,06	★13,06	★13,25	★13,44	★13,87	★13,81
Greece	★8,646	★8,8	★8,831	★8,982	★9,849	★10,26
Hungary	★9,59	★10,06	★9,805	★9,789	★9,768	★10,12
Ireland	★11,41	★11,93	★12,44	★12,17	★13,42	★13,52
Italy	★8,385	★8,502	★8,614	★8,781	★8,852	★8,779
Latvia	★10,59	★10,75	★10,41	★9,977	★10,22	★10,28
Lithuania	★9,793	★10,22	★10,88	★10,93	★11,27	★11,54
Luxembourg	★12,33	★13,03	★13,12	★13,32	★14,01	★14,05
Malta	★12,71	★11,61	★12,58	★13,35	★12,47	★12,27
Netherlands	★13,22	★14,07	★14,69	★14,87	★15,2	★15,39
Poland	★7,858	★8,618	★8,975	★9,128	★9,067	★9,425
Portugal	★9,922	★9,962	★10,1	★10,3	★11,12	★11,39
Romania	★7,378	★7,417	★7,503	★7,557	★7,907	★8,263
Slovakia	★9,857	★10,08	★10,95	★11,06	★10,66	★10,94
Slovenia	★10,98	★11,18	★11,36	★11,57	★11,91	★11,95
Spain	★11,19	★11,17	★11,29	★11,39	★12	★12,08
Sweden	★14,38	★14,43	★15,89	★15,93	★15,88	★16,14

Human Capital con Competenze Digitali in Europa					
Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Finland</i>	17,78	15	<i>Czechia</i>	11,79
2	<i>Sweden</i>	16,14	16	<i>Croatia</i>	11,68
3	<i>Netherlands</i>	15,39	17	<i>Lithuania</i>	11,54
4	<i>Denmark</i>	15,30	18	<i>Portugal</i>	11,39
5	<i>Estonia</i>	14,48	19	<i>Slovakia</i>	10,94
6	<i>Luxembourg</i>	14,05	20	<i>Latvia</i>	10,28
7	<i>Germany</i>	13,81	21	<i>Greece</i>	10,26
8	<i>Ireland</i>	13,52	22	<i>Hungary</i>	10,12
9	<i>Austria</i>	13,34	23	<i>Cyprus</i>	9,92
10	<i>Belgium</i>	12,70	24	<i>Poland</i>	9,42
11	<i>Malta</i>	12,27	25	<i>Italy</i>	8,78
12	<i>Spain</i>	12,08	26	<i>Romania</i>	8,26
13	<i>Slovenia</i>	11,95	27	<i>Bulgaria</i>	8,18
14	<i>France</i>	11,84			

Human Capital con Competenze Digitali in Europa nel 2021

Variazione del valore capitale umano tra il 2016 ed il 2021

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Poland</i>	1,567	19,940	15	<i>Finland</i>	1,394	8,509
2	<i>Greece</i>	1,615	18,675	16	<i>Spain</i>	0,889	7,942
3	<i>Ireland</i>	2,106	18,452	17	<i>France</i>	0,850	7,738
4	<i>Lithuania</i>	1,743	17,798	18	<i>Belgium</i>	0,778	6,529
5	<i>Netherlands</i>	2,165	16,373	19	<i>Germany</i>	0,749	5,734
6	<i>Portugal</i>	1,470	14,813	20	<i>Hungary</i>	0,530	5,527
7	<i>Luxembourg</i>	1,721	13,963	21	<i>Italy</i>	0,394	4,696
8	<i>Sweden</i>	1,758	12,228	22	<i>Cyprus</i>	0,435	4,592
9	<i>Romania</i>	0,885	11,998	23	<i>Austria</i>	0,442	3,429
10	<i>Czechia</i>	1,210	11,437	24	<i>Denmark</i>	0,123	0,809
11	<i>Slovakia</i>	1,081	10,970	25	<i>Bulgaria</i>	-0,051	-0,618
12	<i>Estonia</i>	1,403	10,727	26	<i>Latvia</i>	-0,310	-2,932
13	<i>Croatia</i>	1,083	10,219	27	<i>Malta</i>	-0,432	-3,401
14	<i>Slovenia</i>	0,973	8,862				

Variazione del valore assoluto del capitale umano con competenze digitali tra il 2016 ed il 2021

Variazione del valore percentuale del capitale umano tra il 2016 ed il 2021

$$\text{HumanCapital}_{it} = \text{InternetUserSkills}_{it} + \text{AdvancedSkillsAndDevelopment}_{it}$$

$$\text{InternetUserSkills}_{it}$$

$$= \text{AtLeastBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \text{AboveBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \text{AtLeastBasicSoftwareSkills}_{it}$$

$$\text{AdvancedSkillsAndDevelopment}$$

$$= \text{ICTSpecialists}_{it} + \text{FemaleICTSpecialists}_{it} + \text{EnterprisesProvidingICTTraining}_{it} + \text{ICTGraduates}_{it}$$

Da cui deriva che

$$\text{HumanCapital}_{it} = \text{AtLeastBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \text{AboveBasicDigitalSkills}_{it} + \text{AtLeastBasicSoftwareSkills}_{it} + \text{ICTSpecialists}_{it} + \text{FemaleICTSpecialists}_{it} + \text{EnterprisesProvidingICTTraining}_{it} + \text{ICTGraduates}_{it}$$

Dove $i = 27$ e $t = [2016; 2021]$

